

SLURM Executor Plugin - Support for GPUs

1 Snakemake-Executor-Plugin for SLURM

1.1 Authors

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1.2 Description

- Enhanced GPU Support (v1.0.0): You can now easily request GPUs for your Snakemake workflows using either the [gpu](#) or [gres](#) resource specifications.
- SLURM Account Handling: The plugin automatically attempts to identify your SLURM account. However, we've added the ability to suppress account specification for clusters where users do not have permission to set accounts. This ensures compatibility with a wider range of SLURM configurations.
- Robust Account Detection (v1.0.1): Improved logic for detecting and validating SLURM accounts, resulting in more reliable job submissions.

1.3 References

- [version 1.0.0](#)
- [version 1.0.1](#)